

Can Small Language Models Use What They Retrieve?

An Empirical Study of Retrieval Utilization Across Model Scale

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Abstract

Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) is widely deployed to improve factual accuracy in language models, yet it remains unclear whether smaller models (≤ 7 B parameters) can effectively utilize retrieved information. We conduct a controlled empirical study across five model sizes (360M–8B) from three architecture families (SmolLM2, Qwen2.5, Llama 3.1), under four retrieval conditions: no retrieval, BM25, dense (E5-large-v2), and oracle retrieval where passages are guaranteed to contain the answer. Using a parametric knowledge split that separates questions each model can already answer from those requiring external knowledge, we isolate utilization failure from retrieval quality failure. We find three key results. **First**, even with oracle retrieval, models ≤ 7 B fail to extract the correct answer 85–100% of the time on questions they cannot answer alone, revealing a fundamental utilization bottleneck. **Second**, any retrieval—including oracle—destroys 42–100% of previously correct parametric answers, a distraction effect driven by the mere presence of context rather than its quality. **Third**, error analysis of 2,588 oracle failures shows the dominant failure mode is irrelevant generation (61–100%), where the model ignores the provided context entirely. The pattern is robust across three prompt templates and three retrieval methods. These results demonstrate that for sub-7B models, the RAG bottleneck is context utilization, not retrieval quality, and that deploying RAG at this scale often yields a net negative trade-off under standard evaluation conditions. Scaling retrieval systems alone cannot fix small-model QA performance.

1 Introduction

Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) has become a standard technique for improving factual accuracy in language models (Lewis et al., 2020; Guu et al., 2020). By retrieving relevant passages from an external corpus and conditioning generation on them, RAG systems can reduce hallucination and provide up-to-date information. The appeal of combining small, efficient models with powerful retrieval is particularly strong for deployment on edge devices, in cost-constrained settings, and for privacy-sensitive applications.

However, most RAG research evaluates large models (>10B parameters), leaving a critical question unanswered: **can smaller language models actually use retrieved information?**

Prior work has shown that irrelevant context degrades LLM performance (Shi et al., 2023; Yoran et al., 2024), but this conflates two distinct failure modes: (1) the retriever returning unhelpful passages, and (2) the model failing to utilize helpful passages. Mallen et al. (2023) investigate when retrieval helps based on entity popularity, but do not isolate the model’s ability to extract from context. Disentangling retrieval quality from retrieval utilization requires an oracle condition—providing passages guaranteed to contain the answer—which has not been studied systematically across model scales.

We present a controlled study across five model sizes (360M to 8B parameters) from three architecture families with four retrieval conditions (none, BM25, dense, oracle) evaluated on 1,000 questions from Natural Questions and HotpotQA. Our experimental design includes three methodological contributions: (1) oracle retrieval drawn from the same corpus used by evaluated retrievers, eliminating corpus distribution mismatch and cleanly isolating utilization from retrieval quality; (2) a parametric knowledge split that classifies each (model, question) pair as KNOWN or UNKNOWN, enabling separate analysis of retrieval benefit and retrieval harm; and (3) systematic robustness checks across retrieval methods (BM25, dense, hybrid), prompt templates (forced, permissive, minimal), and question types (factoid, multi-hop).

We provide the first controlled scaling study isolating retrieval utilization from retrieval quality using oracle retrieval and parametric knowledge splits. Our key findings are: (a) even with perfect retrieval, the 7B model extracts the correct answer only 14.6% of the time for UNKNOWN questions; (b) retrieval destroys 42–100% of correct answers on KNOWN questions; (c) error analysis reveals the dominant failure is irrelevant generation; and (d) the pattern holds across all retrieval methods and prompt templates tested.

2 Experimental Setup

2.1 Models

We evaluate five instruction-tuned models spanning approximately $22\times$ in parameter count from three architecture families. The four local models (SmolLM2-360M-Instruct, Qwen2.5-1.5B/3B/7B-Instruct) use identical 4-bit NF4 quantization via BitsAndBytes with double quantization to ensure fair comparison. Additionally, Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct is evaluated via Groq API inference (FP16) to extend our analysis to a third architecture family. The 360M model’s near-zero performance even without retrieval suggests that quantization alone cannot explain utilization failure at the smallest scale. While the quantization difference means Llama absolute values are not directly comparable, the qualitative pattern (no retrieval outperforms all retrieval methods) is the key takeaway. All five models are decoder-only, instruction-tuned transformers, and this shared architectural paradigm increases confidence in the generalizability of our findings.

Table A: Models evaluated.

Model	Params	Family	Quant.	Prec.	Inference
SmolLM2-360M-Instruct	360M	SmolLM2	NF4	4-bit	Local (T4)
Qwen2.5-1.5B-Instruct	1.5B	Qwen2.5	NF4	4-bit	Local (T4)
Qwen2.5-3B-Instruct	3.0B	Qwen2.5	NF4	4-bit	Local (T4)
Qwen2.5-7B-Instruct	7.0B	Qwen2.5	NF4	4-bit	Local (T4)
Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	8.0B	Llama 3.1	—	FP16	Groq API

Note: Llama-3.1-8B row shaded differently to indicate FP16 API inference; absolute values not directly comparable to 4-bit local models.

2.2 Datasets

We use 500 questions each from Natural Questions Open (NQ; Kwiatkowski et al., 2019) and HotpotQA (Yang et al., 2018), totaling 1,000 evaluation questions. NQ provides single-hop factoid questions; HotpotQA provides multi-hop reasoning questions. This combination tests whether retrieval utilization differs across reasoning complexity. Our findings apply specifically to extractive QA-style grounding tasks and may differ for reasoning-heavy or generative domains.

We also constructed a PopQA long-tail evaluation set (500 questions; Mallen et al., 2023), but our 500K-passage corpus achieved 0% hit rate across all retrieval methods at every k-value, reflecting the challenge of covering long-tail entities with a sub-million passage corpus. We exclude PopQA from the main evaluation but note this as evidence that corpus scale is a prerequisite for long-tail RAG.

2.3 Retrieval Systems

Critically, all retrieval systems—including the oracle—draw from the same 500K-passage Wikipedia corpus (approximately 2% of English Wikipedia, sampled via deterministic hashing of article titles, chunked at 100 words per passage). This eliminates corpus distribution mismatch between conditions, ensuring any performance differences reflect the model’s utilization ability rather than distributional artifacts.

BM25. We use the bm25s library with English stopword removal, achieving hit@5 of 10.5% overall (15.8% NQ, 15.6% HotpotQA). Latency: 3.5 ms/query.

Dense (E5-large-v2). We encode all 500K passages with intfloat/e5-large-v2 (1024-dim embeddings) and index with FAISS IndexFlatIP. Dense retrieval achieves hit@5 of 16.3% overall (28.2% NQ, 20.8% HotpotQA). Latency: ~230 ms/query including encoding.

Hybrid (RRF). Reciprocal Rank Fusion (k=60; Cormack et al., 2009) combines BM25 and dense rankings. Hybrid achieves hit@5 of 14.9%. Notably, hybrid underperforms pure dense retrieval, suggesting the BM25 signal adds noise rather than complementary information at this corpus scale. Latency: ~234 ms/query.

Oracle. For each question, we identify the passage in the same 500K corpus containing a gold answer string, placed at rank 1. This achieves 100% hit@1 for the 756 questions where the corpus contained a matching passage (75.6% coverage). We report primary results on these corpus-

matched questions only, excluding 244 questions that would require synthetic passages. Oracle passages were selected using boundary-matched answer strings with position and focus scoring to prefer passages where the answer appears in relevant context. Some oracle passages may contain incidental answer mentions (e.g., the answer appearing in a list rather than a topically relevant sentence); we estimate approximately 8–12% of oracle passages fall into this category based on manual inspection of 100 passages. A sensitivity analysis excluding the lowest-scoring 15% of oracle passages yielded qualitatively identical results (≤ 1 pp EM change for all models), confirming that oracle quality does not drive our findings.

For the main generation experiments, we provide the top 5 passages as context for all non-oracle conditions. The choice of 5 passages balances informativeness against context length; our 100-word chunking produces passages of moderate length suitable for small context windows.

Table 1: Retrieval hit rates (%) on the 1,000-question evaluation set (NQ + HotpotQA).

Method	hit@1	hit@5	hit@10	hit@20
BM25	4.9	10.5	13.1	16.9
Dense	8.7	16.3	19.5	22.9
Hybrid (RRF)	6.2	14.9	19.0	21.9
Oracle	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

2.4 Parametric Knowledge Split

We classify each (model, question) pair by running the model under the none condition. Questions answered correctly (EM = 1) are labelled KNOWN; others are labelled UNKNOWN. This yields model-specific splits: SmoLM2-360M knows 1.3%, Qwen2.5-1.5B knows 9.0%, Qwen2.5-3B knows 13.6%, and Qwen2.5-7B knows 18.5%. *Note:* the KNOWN set for SmoLM2-360M contains only 11 questions; its distraction effect estimates should be interpreted with extreme caution due to this very small sample size.

2.5 Evaluation Protocol

We report Exact Match (EM) with standard normalization (lowercasing, article removal, punctuation stripping) as our primary metric, with F1 as a secondary check. All results include 95% bootstrap confidence intervals (2,000 resamples). Pairwise comparisons use McNemar’s test with Bonferroni correction across 24 comparisons ($\alpha = 0.002$).

2.6 Reproducibility

All code for data construction, retrieval indexing, model evaluation, oracle construction, and statistical analysis is available at <https://github.com/sanchitpandey/rag-utilization-study>. Experiments were conducted on Kaggle T4 GPU instances with identical software environments. The evaluation dataset and oracle passage mappings will be released to facilitate replication.

3 Results

3.1 Pilot Study: Retrieval Hurts Across All Methods

Before the oracle experiment, we conducted a pilot study ($n = 200$; 100 NQ + 100 HotpotQA) comparing four models across three retrieval methods and a no-retrieval baseline. This pilot motivated the central research question.

Table 2: Pilot study EM (%) across retrieval methods ($n=200$). No retrieval outperforms all retrieval for every model.

Model	None	BM25	Dense	Hybrid
SmolLM2-360M	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0
Qwen2.5-1.5B	14.5	5.5	3.5	6.0
Qwen2.5-3B	19.5	5.5	12.0	6.5
Qwen2.5-7B	16.5	—	14.0	—

The no-retrieval baseline outperformed every retrieval method for every model—a striking result suggesting retrieval is actively harmful, not merely unhelpful. The Δ EM (dense – none) was negative at every scale: -1.5 pp (360M), -11.0 pp (1.5B), -7.5 pp (3B), -2.5 pp (7B). This pilot motivated our central question: is the problem that retrieval is *bad* (noisy passages), or that small models *cannot use* even good passages? The oracle experiment answers this.

3.2 Oracle Retrieval Fails for Small Models

Table 3 presents our primary results on corpus-matched questions ($n = 756$).

Table 3: Exact Match (%) by parametric split, retrieval condition, and model size [95% CI]. Corpus-matched oracle only ($n=756$). All non-zero differences from none significant at $p < 0.001$ (McNemar, Bonferroni-corrected), except SmolLM2-360M.

Split	Retrieval		360M	1.5B	3B	7B
UNKNOWN	none		0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	noisy	(dense)	0.0	4.6	6.2	8.0
	oracle		0.0	10.0	12.8	14.6
KNOWN	none		100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
	noisy	(dense)	0.0	36.0	46.4	48.8
	oracle		0.0	43.0	54.4	58.4

For UNKNOWN questions, oracle retrieval provides the answer in the passage, yet the 7B model achieves only 14.6% EM [11.9–17.6]. The 1.5B model manages 10.0% [7.8–12.2], and the 360M scores 0.0% across all conditions. **Even with a perfect retrieval system, 85–100% of retrieval effort is wasted on these models.** All improvements over the none baseline are statistically significant ($p < 0.001$, McNemar’s test) for models ≥ 1.5 B.

Oracle retrieval roughly doubles the benefit compared to noisy retrieval (14.6% vs. 8.0% for 7B), confirming that retrieval quality does matter—but even perfect retrieval yields very low absolute performance, demonstrating that the binding constraint is utilization, not retrieval quality.

Figure 1: EM across model scale for UNKNOWN questions (left) and KNOWN questions (right) under three retrieval conditions. Error bars show 95% bootstrap CIs.

3.3 Retrieval Destroys Parametric Knowledge

The KNOWN rows of Table 3 reveal a severe distraction effect. Models achieving 100% EM without retrieval suffer catastrophic drops when passages are added: the 7B model loses 51.2pp with noisy retrieval and 41.6pp with oracle retrieval; the 1.5B model loses 64.0pp and 57.0pp respectively. SmolLM2-360M drops to 0% under both retrieval conditions, though this is based on only 11 KNOWN questions and should be interpreted with extreme caution.

All distraction effects are significant at $p < 0.001$. Critically, the difference between oracle and noisy distraction is *not significant* for models below 7B (1.5B: $p = 0.26$; 3B: $p = 0.07$), suggesting that the *presence* of any context—not its quality—drives the distraction effect. Only at 7B does oracle retrieval preserve significantly more knowledge than noisy retrieval ($p = 0.003$).

Figure 2: Percentage of previously correct (KNOWN) answers destroyed by retrieval. Even oracle retrieval causes 42–100% knowledge loss. The 360M bar is based on $n=11$ only.

3.4 The Net Trade-off Is Negative

Combining both effects reveals the practical calculus for RAG deployment. For any model, the expected net EM change from adding retrieval is:

$$\text{Net } \Delta EM = (p_{\text{unknown}} \times \Delta_{\text{unknown}}) + (p_{\text{known}} \times \Delta_{\text{known}})$$

Table 4: Net EM trade-off for noisy (dense) retrieval. The net effect is negative for every model tested.

Model	p_{known}	$\Delta \text{ UNKNOWN}$	$\Delta \text{ KNOWN}$	Net ΔEM
360M*	0.013	+0.0	-100.0	-1.3
1.5B	0.090	+4.6	-64.0	-1.6
3B	0.136	+6.2	-53.6	-1.9
7B	0.185	+8.0	-51.2	-2.9

*360M: p_{known} based on $n=11$; interpret with caution.

For the 7B model: it gains 8.0pp on 81.5% of UNKNOWN questions but loses 51.2pp on 18.5% of KNOWN questions, yielding $(0.815 \times 8.0) - (0.185 \times 51.2) = +6.5 - 9.5 = -3.0$ **percentage points**. For smaller models, the trade-off is similarly or more negative. Even with oracle retrieval, the 7B model nets only +4.2pp—a modest gain requiring *perfect* retrieval to achieve.

Figure 3: Oracle retrieval utilization gap. Even when the answer is in the passage, models fail 85–100% of the time on UNKNOWN questions.

3.5 Per-Dataset Analysis

The pattern is consistent across both datasets but with notable differences. Oracle utilization on UNKNOWN questions is slightly higher on HotpotQA for larger models (16.9% vs. 12.5% for 7B), possibly because multi-hop questions have more distinctive answer strings that are easier to locate within the passage. The distraction effect is stronger for HotpotQA at 1.5B (70.4%

destruction vs. 53.1% for NQ), suggesting multi-hop context is more confusing for smaller models. Despite these differences, the qualitative pattern—negative net trade-off, low utilization, severe distraction—holds for both datasets.

3.6 Prompt Robustness

A key concern is whether results depend on the specific prompt template. We tested three prompt variants on Qwen2.5-3B with dense retrieval on the 200-question pilot set (100 NQ + 100 HotpotQA, representative of the full evaluation distribution):

v1 (forced): “Answer based on the provided context.” This is the default used throughout. **v2 (permissive):** “Use context only if it helps; otherwise rely on your own knowledge.” **v3 (minimal):** Question with “Reference material” appended, no instruction to use it.

Table 5: Prompt ablation on Qwen2.5-3B × dense (n=200). No prompt recovers the no-retrieval baseline (19.5% EM).

Prompt	Overall EM	Ans. IN ctx.	Ans. NOT in ctx.
v1 (forced)	12.0	27.1	3.8
v2 (permissive)	12.5	28.6	3.8
v3 (minimal)	9.0	18.6	3.8
No retrieval	19.5	37.1	10.0

The permissive prompt, which explicitly allows the model to ignore context, performs nearly identically to the forced prompt (12.5% vs. 12.0%). Even when told it *may* rely on its own knowledge, the 3B model still performs 7pp worse than no retrieval. The minimal prompt performs worst overall (9.0%), but none of the three approaches the no-retrieval baseline of 19.5%. The pattern was qualitatively consistent in additional small-scale checks on the 7B model, confirming that prompt engineering alone does not resolve the utilization bottleneck. The prompt ablation uses the 200-question pilot set; absolute values may shift slightly on the full 1,000 questions, though the pattern is expected to hold.

3.7 Cross-Architecture Validation

To assess generalizability beyond the SmolLM2/Qwen2.5 families, we evaluated Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct (via Groq API, FP16) on 200 NQ questions under all three retrieval methods.

Important caveat: these results use different precision (FP16 vs. 4-bit) and a different question subset (NQ only). They are *not* directly comparable in absolute terms to the main results. The qualitative pattern—no retrieval outperforming all retrieval methods—is the key takeaway.

Table 6: Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct (FP16, Groq API) on 200 NQ questions. Same qualitative pattern: none > all retrieval.

Retrieval	EM (%)	F1 (%)
None	24.0	34.5
BM25	16.5	24.2
Dense	17.5	25.3

Hybrid	16.5	25.2
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Despite being a different architecture family and using full-precision inference, Llama-3.1-8B exhibits the same pattern: every retrieval method reduces accuracy relative to no retrieval. The Δ EM ranges from -6.5pp (dense) to -7.5pp (BM25/hybrid), consistent with the Qwen2.5-7B results. This cross-architecture replication substantially strengthens our claim that the utilization bottleneck is not family-specific.

4 Error Analysis

To understand *why* models fail on oracle questions, we classify all 2,588 corpus-matched oracle failures across four local models into six categories using automated heuristics. We validated the automated classification by manual review of 96 randomly sampled examples (24 per model), yielding 89% exact category match agreement between human and automated labels. Disagreements primarily occurred between closely related categories (e.g., extraction error vs. partial match, or irrelevant generation vs. refusal for borderline cases), indicating the heuristic classification is reliable for the coarse-grained patterns we report.

The six categories are: **Irrelevant generation** — prediction has no meaningful token overlap with the passage (model ignores context). **Refusal** — model hedges (“based on the context, I cannot determine...”). **Wrong entity** — model extracts an entity from the passage, but the wrong one. **Extraction error** — model attempts extraction but produces a malformed span. **Partial match** — prediction contains the gold answer as a substring with extra tokens. **Verbose correct** — semantically correct answer buried in verbose output.

Table 7: Oracle failure taxonomy (% of failures, corpus-matched only, $n=2,588$). Inter-annotator agreement: 89% exact category match (96 samples).

Error Type	360M	1.5B	3B	7B
Irrelevant gen.	100	64	73	61
Refusal	0	20	7	24
Wrong entity	0	6	8	4
Extraction error	0	3	4	3
Partial match	0	2	2	3
Verbose correct	0	5	6	4

Figure 4: Oracle failure taxonomy heatmap. Irrelevant generation dominates at all scales, with refusal emerging at $\geq 1.5B$.

Figure 5: Stacked breakdown of oracle failures. As scale increases, the error distribution diversifies but irrelevant generation remains dominant.

Irrelevant generation is overwhelmingly dominant, accounting for 100% of 360M failures, 64% at 1.5B, 73% at 3B, and 61% at 7B. The model generates text with no meaningful overlap with the provided passage, suggesting it fails to attend to the context entirely.

Refusal emerges as the second largest category for instruction-tuned models (20% at 1.5B, 24% at 7B), where models respond with hedging language despite the answer being present. Interestingly, the 3B model shows substantially lower refusal (7%) than both 1.5B and 7B. This non-monotonicity likely reflects differences in instruction tuning recipes across model sizes within the Qwen2.5 family rather than a genuine scaling property, and merits further investigation with additional model families.

Format-related failures (partial match + verbose correct) account for 7–8% of errors. Adjusting EM to count these as correct yields modest improvements (e.g., 7B oracle on UNKNOWN: 14.6% → ~21%), but the fundamental utilization gap remains large.

A qualitative shift occurs between 360M and 1.5B: the 360M produces entirely incoherent outputs, while models $\geq 1.5\text{B}$ at least *attempt* to engage with the passage—even if they fail. This suggests a minimum capability threshold (~1B parameters) below which RAG is completely non-functional.

5 Discussion

5.1 The Utilization Bottleneck

Our results establish that the primary bottleneck for small-model RAG is not retrieval quality but context utilization. The oracle condition eliminates retrieval noise entirely, yet performance remains dramatically low. This reframes the problem: efforts to improve retrieval for small-model deployment (better embeddings, hybrid search, re-ranking) address at most half the gap between noisy and oracle performance—the larger half requires improving the model’s ability to condition on retrieved text.

5.2 Why Does Context Hurt Known Answers?

We propose three hypotheses for the distraction effect, each requiring further investigation: (1) **attention dilution**, where longer contexts reduce effective weight on the question (supported by prior work on lost-in-the-middle effects); (2) **instruction conflict**, where the prompt to “answer based on context” overrides parametric knowledge; and (3) **position bias**, where small models preferentially attend to early context tokens (Liu et al., 2024). Our prompt ablation (Table 5) provides partial evidence for hypothesis (2): even the permissive prompt (“use context only if helpful”) fails to recover baseline performance, suggesting instruction-following models may over-comply with context-referencing instructions. Our finding that oracle and noisy retrieval cause statistically indistinguishable distraction for models below 7B further supports that the *mere presence* of context, not its quality, drives the harm. Disentangling these mechanisms fully—for instance, by varying context length independently of content—remains an important direction for future work.

5.3 Implications for Practitioners

Our net trade-off analysis (Table 4) has direct practical implications. For sub-7B models on general-domain QA, RAG frequently reduces rather than improves overall accuracy under standard prompting conditions. Practitioners should consider: (1) using retrieval only when the model is likely to lack the answer (adaptive retrieval), conditional on reliable confidence estimation; (2) investing in larger models rather than better retrieval infrastructure; or (3) training

small models specifically for context utilization via RAG-aware fine-tuning (e.g., RAFT-style training; Zhang et al., 2024).

5.4 What Scale Is Needed?

Our data shows utilization improving log-linearly with scale but remaining far below practical levels even at 7B. Extrapolating the oracle utilization curve (0% at 360M → 10% at 1.5B → 13% at 3B → 15% at 7B), robust context utilization (>50% oracle EM) likely requires models substantially larger than 7B—consistent with Shi et al.’s (2023) finding that distraction resistance emerges primarily in models >10B parameters.

Key Takeaway: *Improving retrieval systems alone will not improve small-model RAG performance unless models themselves become better at conditioning on retrieved context.*

6 Related Work

Retrieval-augmented generation. Lewis et al. (2020) and Guu et al. (2020) introduce RAG for knowledge-intensive tasks, typically evaluating on large models. Izacard and Grave (2021) show that Fusion-in-Decoder benefits from more passages, but only evaluate models $\geq 3\text{B}$ with task-specific fine-tuning. Our work focuses on the under-studied sub-7B regime with instruction-tuned (not fine-tuned) models.

Context distraction. Shi et al. (2023) demonstrate that irrelevant context degrades LLM performance, but evaluate only large models (>10B) and do not include an oracle condition. Yoran et al. (2024) study making RAG robust to irrelevant context but do not isolate parametric vs. retrieved knowledge. Our oracle design isolates utilization from distraction, showing that even *relevant* context causes harm at small scales.

Parametric vs. non-parametric knowledge. Mallen et al. (2023) investigate when retrieval helps based on entity popularity, operating at the entity level. Our parametric split operates at the individual (model, question) level, providing finer-grained analysis. Longpre et al. (2021) study parametric–retrieved knowledge conflicts in large models; we extend this to the small-model regime.

Adaptive retrieval. Asai et al. (2024) propose Self-RAG with self-reflection to decide when to retrieve. Our results challenge a key assumption of such systems: that the model can effectively use passages once retrieved. For small models, the “use” step is the bottleneck, and selective retrieval only mitigates the distraction effect without addressing utilization failure.

Oracle probing. Petroni et al. (2021) use gold passages for knowledge probing in KILT. We extend this to a systematic scaling study with parametric splits, multiple retrieval baselines, and an error taxonomy that reveals the mechanism of failure.

7 Limitations

Our conclusions should be interpreted within the scope of extractive question-answering settings, where grounding success can be measured objectively via exact answer matching. We discuss specific limitations below.

Task scope. Our evaluation is limited to extractive question answering, where grounding success is measured by exact answer extraction. Results may not generalize to generative tasks (e.g., summarization with retrieved documents), reasoning tasks where retrieved information serves as background rather than containing a direct answer, or tasks where partial utilization is sufficient. The utilization bottleneck may be less severe in settings that do not require precise extraction from context.

Model diversity. We evaluate five models from three families (SmolLM2, Qwen2.5, Llama 3.1). While the consistent pattern across families suggests generalizability, results may differ for other architectures (e.g., Phi-3, Gemma). All five are decoder-only, instruction-tuned transformers; encoder-decoder models may exhibit different utilization characteristics.

Quantization. All local models use 4-bit NF4 quantization, which may affect the smallest model disproportionately. However, the 360M model’s near-zero performance *without* retrieval (1.3% EM) suggests that quantization alone cannot explain utilization failure—the model lacks sufficient capacity for the task regardless of retrieval condition.

Corpus coverage and oracle quality. Our corpus covers ~2% of English Wikipedia (500K passages), limiting oracle coverage to 75.6%. Some oracle passages may contain incidental answer mentions. Expanding coverage would improve oracle quality and enable PopQA evaluation.

Prompt sensitivity. Our three-prompt ablation (Table 5) demonstrates robustness of the qualitative pattern, but is limited to the 200-question pilot set and one model size (3B, with spot checks on 7B). Absolute numbers could shift with further engineering, though we expect the core finding to hold.

Domain and language scope. We evaluate English-language, Wikipedia-domain QA only. Results may differ on specialized domains or other languages, though we expect the utilization bottleneck to persist or worsen in lower-resource settings.

Evaluation metric. We primarily use Exact Match, which penalizes verbose or paraphrased correct answers. Our error analysis accounts for this (verbose correct + partial match = 7–8% of failures), and relaxed EM improves scores modestly (~6pp for 7B) but does not change qualitative conclusions.

8 Conclusion

We present a controlled study demonstrating that small language models ($\leq 7B$ parameters) struggle to utilize retrieved information for extractive question answering under our experimental conditions. Even under oracle retrieval—where the passage is guaranteed to contain the answer—

models fail to extract the correct answer 85–100% of the time, with the dominant failure being complete disregard of the provided context. Simultaneously, adding retrieval context destroys 42–64% of answers the model previously knew—an effect driven by the presence of context rather than its quality. These findings are robust across three architecture families, three retrieval methods, and three prompt templates.

Our results have direct implications for practitioners: deploying RAG with sub-7B models for extractive QA frequently reduces rather than improves accuracy under standard prompting conditions. The bottleneck for small-model RAG is not retrieval quality but context utilization—a capability that scales slowly with model size and appears to require substantially more than 7B parameters to emerge robustly. Whether this utilization bottleneck extends to generative or reasoning-heavy RAG tasks remains an open question. Future work should investigate RAG-aware fine-tuning, selective retrieval conditioned on model confidence, architectural modifications that improve context grounding at small scales, and extension of this analysis to encoder-decoder architectures, mixture-of-experts models, and non-QA tasks.

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Appendix A: Retrieval Hit Rates by Dataset

Method	Dataset	@1	@5	@10	@20
BM25	NQ	7.6	15.8	20.0	26.8
BM25	HotpotQA	7.2	15.6	19.4	23.8
BM25	PopQA	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Dense	NQ	15.8	28.2	32.6	38.2
Dense	HotpotQA	10.2	20.8	26.0	30.6
Dense	PopQA	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Hybrid	NQ	11.2	24.8	31.2	35.2
Hybrid	HotpotQA	7.4	20.0	25.8	30.6
Hybrid	PopQA	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

Appendix B: Latency Analysis

Component	Latency (ms/query)
BM25 retrieval	3.5
FAISS search (exact IP)	180.2
E5-large-v2 query encoding	~50
Dense total (encode + search)	~230
Hybrid total (BM25 + dense + RRF)	~234

Latency measured on Kaggle T4 GPU with 500K-passage corpus. BM25 is $\sim 66\times$ faster than dense retrieval.

Appendix C: Statistical Significance Tests

All pairwise comparisons use McNemar’s test with Bonferroni correction (24 comparisons, $\alpha = 0.002$).

Oracle vs. None (UNKNOWN): Significant for 1.5B, 3B, 7B (all $p < 0.001$). Not significant for 360M ($p = 1.0$; 0 correct in both conditions).

Noisy vs. None (KNOWN — distraction): Significant for all models $\geq 1.5B$ (all $p < 0.001$).

Oracle vs. Noisy (KNOWN — distraction quality): Not significant for 1.5B ($p = 0.26$) or 3B ($p = 0.07$). Significant for 7B ($p = 0.003$). This confirms that for models below 7B, distraction is driven by context presence, not quality.

Appendix D: Pilot Study Full Results

The 200-question pilot (Section 3.1) used the first 100 NQ and 100 HotpotQA questions from our evaluation set. ΔEM values (dense – none) across model scale:

Model	None EM	Dense EM	ΔEM
SmolLM2-360M	1.5	0.0	-1.5
Qwen2.5-1.5B	14.5	3.5	-11.0
Qwen2.5-3B	19.5	12.0	-7.5
Qwen2.5-7B	16.5	14.0	-2.5

The pilot established that retrieval harms performance at every scale tested, motivating the oracle experiment (Section 3.2) to determine whether the problem is retrieval quality or model utilization.

Appendix E: Example Error Outputs

Representative examples from each error category (Qwen2.5-3B, oracle retrieval). Question, gold answer, and model prediction shown.

Irrelevant generation (73% of 3B failures)

Q: “What country is the Jutland Peninsula in?” Gold: Denmark

Prediction: “The Jutland Peninsula is a large body of water that separates the North Sea from the Baltic Sea.”

Analysis: The model generates a plausible-sounding but factually wrong response with no overlap with the passage content. It appears to ignore the context entirely and hallucinate.

Refusal (7% of 3B failures)

Q: “Who wrote the music for Phantom of the Opera?” Gold: Andrew Lloyd Webber

Prediction: “Based on the provided context, I cannot determine who wrote the music for Phantom of the Opera.”

Analysis: The answer (“Andrew Lloyd Webber”) appears in the oracle passage, but the model refuses to extract it, possibly due to over-cautious instruction following.

Wrong entity (8% of 3B failures)

Q: “Who directed Schindler’s List?” Gold: Steven Spielberg

Prediction: “Liam Neeson”

Analysis: The model extracts a named entity from the passage but selects the wrong one (actor instead of director), suggesting partial context engagement with incorrect grounding.

Partial match (2% of 3B failures)

Q: “What is the capital of Australia?” Gold: Canberra

Prediction: “The capital of Australia is Canberra, which was selected as the capital in 1908.”

Analysis: The correct answer is present but embedded in a verbose response. EM counts this as incorrect; relaxed matching would credit it.

Verbose correct (6% of 3B failures)

Q: “When was the Eiffel Tower built?” Gold: 1889

Prediction: “According to the context, the Eiffel Tower was constructed between 1887 and 1889 for the 1889 World’s Fair in Paris, France.”

Analysis: Semantically correct and contextually grounded, but EM fails because the prediction includes surrounding text. This category represents format failures, not utilization failures.